

OROONYKONIMS OF SAMARKAND REGION AND THEIR TOPONYMIC ANALYSIS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590952>

Valieva Shakhnoza Islamovna

Samarkand State University

Department of Geography and Natural Resources,

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Abstract: *The article gives an oronymic characteristic of the oikonyms of Samarkand region. Each of these oroikonyms was studied in the context of districts.*

Keywords: *oikonym, oronym, mountain, say, plain, hill, ravine*

Oikonyms are used in relation to cities, villages, auls, and other settlements. Oikonyms (*placenames*) is the most volatile branch of toponymy, which reflects the peculiarities of the nature of the region, the events of historical eras that occurred on the territory, the names of the professions of the population, the names of the clan tribe, depending on the ethnic composition that lived in the area. Settlements are a socio-economic category, and it is of great scientific and practical importance to study the regularities of the formation, location, and naming of cities and villages in close connection with specific natural, historical and political conditions.

Toponymist S. Koraev (2006) considers it expedient to study the names of settlements by dividing them into 2 large groups. These are:

- physical and geographical oikonyms.
- socio-economic oikonyms.

Physical or physical and geographical oikonyms are understood as the names of geographical areas depending on the names of water bodies - hydronyms, geomorphological forms of the area - oronyms, plant names - phytooikonyms, animal names - zooikonyms, and other physical and geographical conditions.

Socio-economic oikonyms associated with the economic activities of people include professional names of people, clan and tribal names-ethnonyms, names associated with first name and surnames, nicknames of people, anthroponyms, religious names-agionyms [3;4].

Later, P. Gulomov (1994) proposed a two-stage system of classification of geographical names. The scientist first divided the toponyms into large groups, and then determined the types of toponyms within each large group and, according to them, divided the toponyms into the next three large groups [5;6].

- Names that appear depending on the natural characteristics of the place.

➤ Names that appear in connection with socio-economic, and political circumstances.

➤ Legendary and strange names.

While studying about the orookonyms of Samarkand region, first of all, let's describe oronym and orookonym. According to the definition of the toponymist S. Koraev (2006), "*oronyms*" include not only mountains, rocks, hills, adyrs, hills, but also negative landforms - such as valleys, gorges, ravines, valleys of sai, depressions, as well as plains, lowlands and sandy massifs. Geographical terms such as adyr, aqba (*mountain pass*), ovga (*mountain pass*), bel (*saddle*), dara (*gorge*), dovon (*mountain pass*), jar (*ravine*), jailow (high mountain pastures), tov-tog (*mountain*), tosh (*stone*), choqqi (*peak*), qir (*upland*), qorgon (*mound*) play an important role in the lexicon of oronyms. Among the oronymic terms, the word tosh (*stone*) has special significance in color symbols such as oq (*white*), qora (*black*), qongir (*brown*).

Sometimes we can find the above oronymic terms in oikonoms. Such oikonoms associated with the structure, and the level of the Earth's relief are called orookonyms (*orographical placenames*). The composition of orookonyms includes such indicators as adyr, bel (*saddle*), jar (*ravine*), tepa (*hill*), tosh (*stone*), tog (*mountain*), qir (*upland*), qum (*sand*).

The following orookonyms of Samarkand region can be referred to as such place names. In Samarkand region, the most common term that has passed from oronymic indicators to oikonoms is "tepa" (*hill*). A "tepa" (*hill*) is a hilly, elevated dome-shaped place with steep slopes, on which in ancient times, for defensive purposes, people-built settlements near the hills, that is, they served to anticipate enemy danger and warn others from it [5]. In the region there are: Aygirtepa, Bobotepa, Jomboytepa, Navroztepa (in Jomboy district), Alqartepa, Devontepa, Farmontepa, Qarovultepa, Qoratepa, Oqtepa, Chambiltepa (in Bulungur district), Jalpoqtepa, Jartepa, Jorabtepa, Mozortepa, Sariqtepa, Choshtepa (in Urgut district), Yogontepa, Oqtepa, Mayintepa (in Qoshrabot district), Dostitepa, Koktepa, Yurgantepa, Kartepa, Uchtepa, Kultepa, Tangitepa (in Ishtixon district), Dovtepa, Yaloqtepa, Choshtepa (in Payariq district), Imomtepa (in Nurobod district), Isovoytepa (in Kattaqorgon district), Kamoltepa, Oqtepa, Zindontepa (in Oqdaryo district), Sartepa (in Samarqand district).

There are also geographical names in which the oronymic term "*jar*" (*ravine*) participates, such names indicate the presence of a ravine with a negative relief form in the immediate vicinity of the village [1]. *Jar* (*ravine*) is a depression formed by the erosion of soft rock by sewage water. *Jar* is also used in the sense of a depression, a lowering. Examples of orookonyms containing the term jar are such place names as Jar (in Payariq, Urgut, Bulungur, Oqdaryo, and Pstdargom districts), Jarboshi, Jomonjar (in Payarik district), Jarquduq (in Nurobod district), Jartepa, Jarqishloq (in Urgut district), Jarosti (in Ishtikhan district), Jarbota (in Oqdaryo district).

Village names such as Toshariq, Toshloq, Toshquduq, Qoratosh of Nurobod, Oqdaryo, Urgut, Jomboy, and Qoshrobot districts of Samarkand region contain the term "*tosh*" (*stone*), and these oikonyms also belong to the geomorphological group of oikonyms. *Tosh* (*stone*), contained in these orooikonyms, is a hard rock and is used in the names of rocky peaks in mountains as well as in place names. For example, there are oronyms with the indicator "qoya" (*rock*), such as Ayriqoya, Belbogliqoya, Qizilqoya (in Urgut district), Qatorqoya (in Qoshrobot district).

Oronyms, with the indicator "tog" (*mountain*), are quite significant in the region and are found in the names of such places as Buqchaqirtog (in Nurabad district), Gardantog, Yettiqiztog (in Urgut district), Gubdintog (in Bulungur district).

In the study area, we can also find place names such as Soy, Joyisoy, Kattasoy, Murodsoy, Oltinsoy, Oqsoy, Tollisoy, Omondara, Chuqur, Qir. The words soy (*sai gully*), dara (*gorge*), qir (*upland*), chuqur (*depression*) in the composition of such orooikonyms are considered oronymic terms denoting the shape of the relief, and under the soy-valley, tributary, former river-bed, flat ravine are understood as hollow areas of the earth's crust formed in various ways. "*Dara*" (*gorge*) is a mountain corridor in the mountains, formed by a tectonic fault, the washing away of hard rocks by rivers. Sometimes dara (*gorge*) is also called vodi (valley), soylik (valley of sai). Qir (*upland*) are flat or gentle domed hills, flat low mountains. They are formed as a result of mountain runoff, wind erosion, and tectonic uplift. The above-mentioned orooikonyms are significant in that they do not change over time.

In general, oronyms are part of separate toponymy that represents the physical and geographical objects associated with the relief structure of the earth. Oronyms are onomastic unit, meaning interconnection, and integral unity of nature and society. Also, the oronyms of Samarkand region are unique in their climatic and natural, location, flora, fauna, natural resources, and geomorphological features.

REFERENCES

1. Akhmadaliev Yu.I. (2009) *Fargona viloyati toponimlari* [Toponyms of Fergana region]. Fergana. p. 187. (in Uzbek)
2. Temirov.Sh.A. (2019) *Samarqand viloyati oronimlarining lisoniy tadqiqi* [Linguistic study of oronyms of Samarkand region] (PhD Thesis abstract), Samarkand. p. 52. (in Uzbek)
2. Qoraev S. (2005) *O'zbekiston viloyatlari toponimlari. O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi*. [Toponyms of the regions of Uzbekistan. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan.]. Tashkent: State Scientific Publishing House. (in Uzbek)
3. Qoraev S. (2006) *Toponimika* [Toponymy]. Tashkent: Publishing House of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan. (in Uzbek)

4. Gulomov P.N. (1994) *Jug'rofiya atamalari va tushunchalari izohli lug'ati* [Glossary of geographical terms and concepts.] Tashkent: Oqituchi. p. 115. (in Uzbek)
5. Khakimov Q. (2016) *Toponimika* [Toponymy]. Tashkent: Mumtoz soz. p. 176. (in Uzbek)